

PROPERTIES OF HIGH IMPACT MODIFIED PLA AND PLA -FLAX COMPOUNDS

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SUMMARY

PLA compounds with various impact modifier classes were tested and improvements in charpy impact strength up to factors of 10 were achieved with new Core-Shell type modifiers opening the non break area for PLA. Reinforcements with flax fibers increased tensile properties and dimensional stability on costs of toughness.

Keywords: PLA, Impact modifier, Flax fibers

INTRODUCTION

In recent years Poly-(lactic acid) as a green polymer has attracted scientific and industrial attention since PLA can be processed similar to polyolefins and is known to be biodegradable. Its good mechanical properties e.g. high stiffness and high tensile strength combined with optical good properties (transparency) made PLA successful in many packing and household applications, but due to the low dimensional stability big markets are still prohibited. In order to make PLA e.g. feasible for automotive industry or other high performance markets new composites need to be developed to overcome the low dimensional stability and improve toughness. In the past different attempts with reinforcements like jute¹, microcrystalline cellulose (MCC)² or flax³ have been made to improve tensile properties in general on costs of impact strength. Recent studies on impact modification of PLA already showed an increase of toughness using natural rubber^{4,5} or commercial petrol based impact modifiers⁶. The goal of this study was to improve impact properties with different commercial available additives as well to improve thermal stability of PLA by incorporating flax fibers.

EXPERIMENTAL

Compounding

The compounds were created in a parallel twin screw extruder (Prism TSE 24 HC) with a screw length of 28D and gravimetric side feeder system for adding the additives and fibers, which were pelletized in a Kahl laboratory before compounding. The neat PLA grade was dried for eight hours in a Motan Luxor 120 at a temperature of 60°C and the Flax fibers were dried in an oven before compounding for eight hours at a temperature of 80°C.

Sample testing

Dog-bone shaped specimens for mechanical tests were moulded in an injection moulding machine (Engel ES 80) and used in tensile tests. Samples for Charpy Impact tests were cut from these dog-bone specimens into rectangular shape of 80x10x4mm with the aid of a custom made Haidlmair pneumatic sample chopper.

Tensile tests were performed in a universal testing machine (Zwick TC-FR020 TH) at a crosshead speed of 5mm/ min and the unnotched Charpy Impact strength determined in a Charpy Impact tester Zwick 5113.300 according to the ISO standards ISO-527-2 and ISO-179 respectively.

The heat deflection temperature (HDT) measurements were performed in a Coesfeld Vicat/HDT tester according to DIN EN ISO 75-2 on rectangular shaped specimen of the dimensions 80x10x4mm with a fiber stress of 1.82MPa (HDT-A) and a heating rate of 2 °C/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PLA –compounds of commercial petrol based impact modifiers such as E-MA-GMA (ethylene- maleic acid- glycidyl methacrylate) or E-CoPo (Ethylene Copolymer) based types as well as core-shell types with contents of 5%, to 30% were created in a parallel twin-screw extruder and mechanically tested according to ISO standards for composites and plastic. The results were plotted in a diagram Charpy impact strength versus Young's modulus to summarize the mechanical properties (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Overview of the mechanical properties of different PLA-Flax composites, neat PLA grade and PLA –Impact modified compounds.

The quality of the individual impact modifier classes of PLA can clearly be seen in Figure 1, where E-CoPo give an improvement of more than a factor 3-5 followed by the E-MA-GMA types with an increase of a factor up to almost 8 but outperformed by the new core shell types with a factor up to more than 10 in the non-break area already by use of industrial amounts of additive (10%_{wt}).

In order to improve tensile- and HDT-properties additional PLA-compounds incorporating chopped flax fibers were created. The flax fibers had an initial length of 4mm and were pelletized in a Kahl laboratory pelletizer in order to feed the fibers into the compounder. The fiber degradation along the individual processing steps was qualitatively evaluated by optical microscopy (Figure 2). In the case of the compounds the fibers were extracted by a cooking the compounds in a Soxhlet extractor for 4.5h using CCl₄ as a solvent. As can be seen in Figure 2 a degradation of the fiber during processing is visible but still longer fibers in the range of 1-2mm (initial length 4mm) can be found in the compounds or even after injection moulding, where the fiber lengths are about 1-1.5 mm, which guarantee the reinforcement of PLA.

Figure 2 – Degradation of Flax fiber length during processing: Optical micrographs of pelletized flax fibers (top-left), flax fibers after compounding (top-right) and flax fibers after injection moulding (bottom left).

In general, the flax fibers reduce impact properties of the modified PLA compounds but they are still higher than compared to the unmodified PLA flax composites or the neat PLA. Of all the tested impact modifiers the E-MA-GMA type of impact modifier is the most effect full one in combination with the fibers, because it increased both, toughness and tensile and HDT properties compared to the unmodified PLA-flax fiber compounds, whereas the other impact modifiers only show slight increase in impact properties compared to PLA-flax fiber compounds (Figure 3). For PLA flax compounds the maximum dimensional stability was achieved after an annealing step of one hour at a temperature of 100°C.

Figure 3 – Impact properties of PLA-Flax composites and PLA –impact modified-Flax compounds.

Additional SEM measurements (Figure 4) performed on these compounds revealed that some of the used impact modifiers also act as coupling agents to the natural fibers (flax), which explains the better mechanical performance compared to the non modified PLA-Flax compounds (Figure 3). A comparison of SEM pictures between PLA-Flax, PLA-IM (E-MA-GMA)-Flax and PLA- IM-Flax (Core-shell) compounds reveal that PLA-IM (E-MA-GMA)-Flax compounds show good fiber matrix adhesion indicated by the “strings” connecting the fibers with the matrix, which results in a better performance in impact behavior (Figure 3) since additional energy can be consumed by fiber pull out processes compared to the unmodified PLA-Flax compound. The core shell impact modified PLA-flax compounds show a good matrix modification, but poor fiber-matrix adhesion, which in the end results in impact properties comparable to the unmodified PLA-Flax compounds.

Figure 4 - SEM micrographs of a PLA-Flax compound (top-left), a PLA-IM-Flax compound (top-right) and a PLA-Core-shell-Flax compound (bottom left).

CONCLUSIONS

The impact properties of Poly lactic acid (PLA) with various impact modifiers increased with the increasing amount of impact modifier content. A ranking of the impact modifier quality gives best performance for the new core shell types followed by the and finally E-CoPo types using industrial amounts of additive. Flax fibers in PLA-IM compounds decrease the impact properties due to the poor fiber performance or poor fiber-matrix adhesion. Only in the case of E-MA-GMA types, a reasonable increase of impact properties was found since they act both ways as impact modifiers for PLA (matrix modifier) as well as a coupling agents for Flax fibers.

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